

Synthesis, Crystal Growth and Characterization of Cu (II) Doped 4 - bromo - 4' - hydroxybenzylidene aniline Nonlinear Optical Material

L. Jothi^{a*}

^bDepartment of Physics, Namakkal Kavignar Ramalingam Government Arts College for Women,
Namakkal-637001, Tamilnadu, India

* Corresponding author:

E-mail: jothilakshmanan@gmail.com

TEL: 9442921205

Abstract

One of the novel benzylidene aniline derivatives, Cu (II) doped 4-bromo- 4'-hydroxybenzylidene aniline (CBHBA) was synthesized and single crystal of CBHBA was grown from solution following slow evaporation method at room temperature. Unit cell parameters of the grown crystal were determined from single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. Functional groups of CBHBA were identified from Fourier Transform Infrared spectral study. UV- Vis - NIR analysis of CBHBA showed that the crystal is transparent between wavelengths 400 and 1100 nm. Thermal stability of the title compound was examined by thermogravimetric and differential scanning calorimetric studies. Fluorescence spectrum of the grown crystal recorded using spectrofluorometer shows emission peak at 450 nm. The second harmonic generation efficiency of CBHBA estimated by Nd:YAG pulsed laser employing the Kurtz powder technique is ~ 1.3 times that of potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate.

Keywords: Organic compounds; Crystal growth; Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy; Thermogravimetric analysis.

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